

MEDICAL SCIENCES

UDC: 615.84; 612.014.42

WAVE THERAPY OF AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS IN CHILDREN USING ELECTRONIC ACTIVATION TECHNOLOGIES

Stekhin A.

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Leading Researcher, National Medical Research Center for Rehabilitation and Balneology of the Russia Ministry of Health, Scopus Author ID–2342631200, RSCI ID – 837609, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8750-0686>

Yakovleva G.

Candidate of Technical Sciences, Senior Researcher, National Medical Research Center for Rehabilitation and Balneology of the Russia Ministry of Health, Scopus Author ID–55863873400, ID RSCI–865322, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8766-2773>

Kalinina L.

doctor – International Consumer Society "MIRAZDRAV", Russia, Moscow, st. Sadovnicheskaya, 5

Karasev A.

International Consumer Society "MIRAZDRAV", Moscow, Sadovnicheskaya St., 5

Rodionov S.

*International Consumer Society "MIRAZDRAV", Moscow, Sadovnicheskaya St., 5
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14959188>*

Abstract

The method of wave therapy for autism spectrum disorders in children, which allows for a therapeutic effect on the nervous and immune systems as the primary link of regulatory mechanisms in the body, is based on the restoration of the charge (electron) state of oxygen carriers in the blood – membranes of erythrocytes and other cells, leading to a restart of cellular regulatory mechanisms and restoration of the energy function of mitochondria. Under the influence of extracellular and intracellular electron donors, the adaptive homeostasis of the body is activated, the normal functioning of the central nervous system is restored, including the restoration of intercenter neural connections of the brain responsible for speech, memory and spatial thinking.

Keywords: associated water, autism spectrum disorders, electron donor activity.

Source of funding: The authors declare no funding for the study.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no obvious or potential conflicts of interest related to the publication of this article.

For correspondence: Anatoly Aleksandrovich Stekhin, PhD in Technical Sciences, Leading Researcher, National Medical Research Center for Rehabilitation and Balneology of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, tel. 8–916–45–96–073, E-mail: Stekhin-aa@mail.ru.

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are complex, dynamic, biological, neurodevelopmental disorders characterized by heterogeneous symptoms, severity, and phenotypes, accompanied by a deficit in social communication and the presence of restricted interests and repetitive behavior [1].

Currently, the pathogenesis of ASD is based on morpho-functional and biochemical models of the main symptoms of this neurodegenerative disease, leading to impaired social communication, restricted and repetitive behavior patterns [2]. When a child is diagnosed with autism, treatment is usually carried out for diseases associated with ASD: insomnia, hyperactivity, irritability and aggression, gastrointestinal disorders, and subclinical epileptiform manifestations [3]. The cause of the disease itself remains unknown, which

predetermines the failure of clinical trials of ASD pharmacotherapy [4]. The main focus in the study of the pathogenesis of ASD is on the relationship between the social-emotional and cognitive development of children with autism spectrum disorder associated with disturbances in the structure of consciousness (theory of mind). The existence of interaction between consciousness and the function of human social, emotional and cognitive skills is associated with neuro-functional disturbances in the structure (or changes in the rate of synthesis) of components of neurotransmitter systems (receptors and carriers), in particular, glutamate, as well as cholinergic, serotonergic, dopaminergic, GABAergic, as well as neurotransmitter metabolism [5], affecting the functioning of the functional neural connection network of the brain (FCN) [6], in particular the frontal-posterior network of regions, including the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (vmPFC) and temporoparietal junction (TPJ) [7], the sensory processing domain of DSM–5, and later ICD–11 [8], responsible for speech, memory and spatial thinking. Neuro-functional impairments in neurodegenerative diseases, ranging from Alzheimer's disease and multiple sclerosis to Parkinson's disease, as well as in neurodevelopmental disorders (autism) may also be caused by coupling of the central nervous system with the enteric nervous system (ENS). Evidence shows that changes in the gut micro-

biome, acting in conjunction with an individual's genetic background, can alter the ENS, the central nervous system and the immune system, impair barrier function and contribute to various disorders such as irritable bowel syndrome, inflammatory bowel disease or neurodegeneration [9].

Creativity in people correlates with the strength of connections between three different brain regions: the executive (responsible for cognitive activity), the default system (cortical–parietal), and the network responsible for the search for relevant stimuli (or salience) [10], which are influenced by the ENS. Among the methods of treating neural activity of the brain, including disorders in the initiation of impulses in the cochlear nerve or disorders in the transmission and conduction of signals along the brainstem, transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS) is used – a non-invasive method of brain stimulation for the cause–and–effect study of the connections between the brain and behavior by inducing changes in the excitability of the cortex [11,12]. However, this method is not aimed at the electronic activation of neural activity of the brain, limiting itself only to electrically conductive structures of the nervous system.

Considering the processes of activation of the neural network, it should be noted that the brain contains about 83% water, respectively, a significant share of its electronically active associated phase [13], which acts as a field regulator of the state of excitation of neurons. Considering that the activation of brain activity is influenced by high–energy states of the associated water phase formed in the processes of electronic activation of water, it is possible to assume the presence of synchronized collective effects of neuronal activation through the excitation of coherent macroscopic oscillations of superconducting current in associates [14], which influence the processes of periodic excitation of neural networks (connectome [15,16]). In this regard, the role of ENS, formed by the pathogenic microbiota of the digestive system, may consist in stimulating low–energy states of water associates, short–chain neural connections, and suppressing the activity of extended intercenter connections.

In this regard, the **aim of the study** is to evaluate the effect of electronic activation of body water on intercentral connections of the brain and the therapeutic effect on autism spectrum syndrome in children.

Equipment and research methods

The method of wave therapy [17,18] was used, which allows for a corrective effect on the functioning of the nervous and immune systems as a key primary link in the wave regulatory mechanisms in the body, based on the restoration of the charge (electron) state of oxygen carriers in the blood – membranes of erythrocytes and other cells, leading to the restart of cellular regulatory mechanisms and the restoration of the energy function of mitochondria. Under the influence of extracellular and intracellular electron donors, the adaptive homeostasis of the body is activated, the normal functioning of the central nervous system is restored, supporting metabolism and restoring the activity of dependent organs and systems of the body. The effectiveness of corrective measures using the wave

therapy method with the use of the MIRA AquaSystem generator equipment (certificate of registration of intellectual property No. 24–1318 dated 12/25/2024 "Device for restoring the electromagnetic field" of the State Standard of Russia; certificate of conformity with regulatory documents ROSS Ru. 32623.0C11 dated 01/13/2025) is confirmed by therapeutic practice and many years of research. The effectiveness of biocorrection, achieved without the use of pharmacological drugs, is at least 85%. The method and methodology of wave therapy using the generator equipment "AquaSystem MIRA" (Certificate of registration of intellectual property No. 24–1319 dated 12/25/2024 "Method of wave therapy ..." of the State Standard of Russia) were created by a team of authors as part of the MPO "MIRAZDRAV" in collaboration with specialists from organizations of the Ministry of Health and the Russian Academy of Sciences. The method implements the latest achievements of world science in the field of water biophysics [13] and quantum technologies in biology and medicine (including the works of Italian experts in the field of quantum electrodynamics Giuliano Preparata and Emilio Del Giudice (until 2014), American cell physiologist and biochemist Gilbert Ling (until 2019)).

Mechanism of action underlying the method

The therapeutic effect, achieved through wave (tunnel) transfer of electrons into the body to oxygen coupling centers in the body's water component (extracellular matrix), is accompanied by an increase in the negative charge of cell membranes and vascular walls, which protects them from the influence of pathogens, changes in metabolic pathways and activation of intracellular biochemical processes. The method ensures activation of systemic and adaptive homeostasis and for this reason is indicated for use in the presence of diseases of metabolic etiology and especially the central nervous and immune systems. The method allows for the effective treatment of somatic, neurological and mental pathologies, and is indicated for post–surgical and chemotherapeutic recovery, intoxications and lesions caused by pathogenic bioagents and other pathologies.

The therapeutic effect of the wave therapy method is based on quantum technologies for the transfer of electrons to the body's water structures, the conversion of electrons into peroxide anion–radicals in the composition of water associates, which have a field (through local electric and magnetic fields) effect on biochemical processes and the excitation of neurons, the initiation of which is associated with the control of keto–enol tautomerism of proteins and conformational transitions of enzyme complexes (works by Gilbert Ling).

Under the influence of field structures generated by peroxide associates, DNA transcription processes are initiated, the ratio of hormonal bioregulators changes, mitotic activity is enhanced, proliferation and differentiation of cells occurs, ensuring the development of normal cells, regeneration and restoration of damaged cells and tissues [19,20], restoration of intercenter connections of the brain and exchange electronic interactions with the environment [13]. Dynamic changes in the state of the body systems of patients (15

people of both sexes with a diagnosis of ASD) were determined by changes in their activity readings after wave correction procedures. The computer program for assessing the level of health "Rhythm-Express" was used based on the analysis of heart rate variability and a mathematical model of the body's development processes. **Results of the study**

The reaction of the body of children with autism spectrum disorders to electronic activation is accompanied by a systemic effect on organs and systems

(table):

– activation of metabolic processes and extra-substrate synthesis of ATP by enzyme complexes of mitochondria of cells, accompanied by bringing the index of tension of regulatory systems of the body to normal values;

– restoration of the electronic state of the central nervous and immune systems, recorded by an increase in the values of their activity;

– greater balance and growth of adaptation reserves of CNS-dependent systems associated with the field control of hormonal regulation.

Dynamic observations of the wave activity of the CNS and ENS (digestive system; stomach) of the body in about 90% of children with ASD, recorded using the Ritm-Express equipment over several correction cycles, indicate negative values of the correlation coefficient (Kcorr.) of their activity. This allows us to state that these systems in children with autism are in a metabolic dependence on each other, which is antagonistic in nature (in the table, these values are highlighted in the background).

Table. Correlation of activity (according to the indications of "Rhythm Express") of body systems in children with a diagnosis of ASD in a series of wave correction procedures (from 1 to 5) using the generator equipment "AquaSystem MIRA"

Systems		Activity (12% is normal), %					
		90% of patients		10% of patients		Isolated cases	
		to	after	to	after	to	after
1	Central nervous	7,5	12,3	7,7	10,8	10,2	9,5
2	Endocrine	7,7	10,9	8,3	10,2	5,2	9,7
3	Respiratory. Autonomic nervous	10,7	6,5	12	8,9	9,1	9,7
4	Digestive. Stomach	10,7	8,6	11,7	10,3	10,6	9,5
5	Cardiovascular	7,5	7,8	5,2	7,2	7,4	6,9
6	Digestive. Intestines	6,5	7,7	5,9	5,2	7,3	6,7
7	Excretory. Kidneys	11,6	8,4	12	9	10,5	9,3
8	Reproductive	12,2	8,6	11,4	9,5	10,5	9,6
9	Arterial. Liver	7,5	7,9	4,5	6	7,3	6,7
10	Musculoskeletal. Gallbladder	7,8	7,8	5,9	7,2	7,3	6,5
11	Venous	8	8,6	9,7	10,4	7,4	9,6
12	Immune. Lymphatic.	7,5	8,6	9,2	9,8	10,2	9,7
	Stress index (50...200), un.	393	97	123	111	799	99
Correlation of system activity in dynamic observations		K _{k1-4} =-0,42... - 0,56		K _{k1-4} =0,99		K _{k1-2} =0,43	
		K _{k1-2} =0,89		K _{k1-6} =-0,46		K _{k1-4} =0,99	

An increase in CNS activity after procedures for electronic activation of the body is accompanied by a decrease in the activity of both the digestive system and the lymphatic system associated with it – the liver. Obviously, as a result of such interaction of systems, mechanisms for suppressing the viability of pathogenic microbiota of the gastrointestinal tract are initiated, which leads to some stress in the liver.

10% of patients with ASD have disorders of the intestinal neurohumoral system. They are not included in the category of ASD disorders and require additional studies to establish an accurate diagnosis. However, the pathogenic microbiome of the gastrointestinal tract is chronic and requires not only electronic activation of the CNS for its neutralization, but also measures to create a symbiotic microbiota. For this purpose, patients were prescribed biologically active drinking water [21] and symbiotics. In one case, in addition to the diagnosis of ASD, a pathological formation (pineal gland cyst) was noted. To eliminate it, the Karasev applicator was used [22], which has proven itself as an effective means of neutralizing benign organ formations.

In some cases, synchronous changes in the wave activity of the CNS and gastrointestinal tract were recorded, characterized by positive values of the correlation coefficient. However, at the same time, there were disorders of the endocrine system, accompanied by extremely high values of the stress index of regulatory systems, increased heart rate and the presence of extrasystoles, which indicates a pathology in this system. Changes in the emotional state observed in this pathology, characterized by sharp mood swings, tearfulness, irritability and other anomalies, can be masked as manifestations of ASD.

According to the results of dynamic observation by the attending physicians, sick children after a series of wave correction and compliance with recommendations became calmer and more emotional, react to others without aggression, show interest in games, and became more sensitive to tactile and vocal stimuli.

Electronic activation of human body systems according to the results of an electroencephalographic study affects the intercenter coordination of neural activity of the brain (Figure).

The initial state of neural connections in a patient with brain pathology (figure on the left) is characterized by a decrease in neural activity in the cerebellum, which plays an important role in the control of movements and in cognitive functions such as attention and language, as well as in the manifestation of fear and

pleasure reactions. There is also a decrease in the activity of neurons in the lateral parietal cortex and the posterior cingulate cortex, which are an important part of the limbic system responsible for the formation and processing of emotions, learning and memory.

Figure. Evaluation of changes in intercenter connections by the electroencephalography (EEG) method using the criterion of cross-pair correlations of signals in the frequency range of 8–13 Hz (alpha rhythm) during wave therapy

After a full course of wave correction (using the "MIRA AquaSystem" and the recommendations for restoring the gastrointestinal microbiota given above), the intercenter connections were saturated with interhemispheric interactions, indicating the restoration of the interhemispheric symmetry of neural excitations responsible for cognitive functions. Obviously, changes in both the reactions of the interacting systems of the body (CNS and digestive system) and the intercenter connections of neurons in the brain to electronic activation of the body indicate the metabolic nature of the causes of autism in children, which predetermines the need to rethink the strategy for treating this type of disease, aimed at eliminating the external causes of their occurrence and development.

Considering the relationship between the gastrointestinal microbiota and the brain, carried out through the channels of wave coupling of the structures of the phase of associated water of the body, autism spectrum disorders in children are associated with the suppression of CNS activity by the ENS.

The therapeutic effect of electronic activation of the body of children with autism, carried out by the generator equipment "AquaSystem MIRA", occurs through the restoration of disrupted neural interactions during the restructuring of the structural organization of the phase of associated water of the body.

Conclusions

1 Autism spectrum disorders in children are associated with changes in metabolism in the gastrointestinal tract, as a result of which the enteric nervous system (microbiome) acquires competitive properties in relation to the weakened CNS.

2 Wave therapy using electronic activation of the body of children with autism, together with measures to create symbiotic microbiota in the gastrointestinal tract, provides effective restoration of interdomain activity of neural networks observed in autism spectrum disorders.

3 Dynamic observations of the CNS and digestive system activity using the Rhythm-Express equipment allow, based on negative values of the correlation coefficients, to diagnose ASD and effectively monitor the course of the disease during wave therapy.

Discussion

The study emphasized the role of body water in establishing spatio-temporal correlations of excitation of the neural network of the brain associated with the structural organization of its associated phase. Unfortunately, the current state of the instrumental base for parameterizing the structural organization of the phase of associated water in the body does not allow its dynamic observations directly in the body. At the same time, the properties of self-similarity and non-locality of the structural organization of the phase [13, 14] identified in previous studies make it possible to project the volumetric properties of water in quantum-conjugate objects.

It is obvious that the body's systems have such communication properties, realized due to the quantum self-similarity of associates in non-local interaction with each other [17–19]. Which is clearly recorded in the present study using the example of the interaction of the CNS and ENS. However, in patients with autism, the interaction of the systems under consideration is not aimed at maintaining each other's activity, but acts in the opposite direction – to suppress activity, which is obviously associated with pathological changes in the phase of associated water in the gastrointestinal tract. Here, for the first time, we emphasize a different understanding of pathology in the system, associated not with biochemical, but with the wave processes occurring in it. It follows from this that the system (in our case, this is the ENS) can function normally in a biochemical sense, but at the same time be in an antagonistic state with the interacting system (CNS) through a shift in the frequency characteristics of wave generation. With re-

gard to autism spectrum disorders, the pathological effect of ENS on interdomain connections in the brain is associated with the induction of altered states of the structural organization of associates in the associated water phase towards their generation of radiation frequencies of other ranges compared to the alpha rhythm (8–13 Hz), which is manifested in EEG studies by a decrease in the intensity of alpha rhythms and sporadic generations of radiation by superconducting structures of the associated water phase at higher frequencies.

Under these conditions, the electronic activation of the body, as a result of which, first of all, the structural organization of the associated water phase is rebuilt with the appearance of high-energy states in it, there is a shift in the generation frequencies of brain structures to the region of lower frequencies and an increase in their intensity. The restoration of intercenter connections, especially interhemispheric electronic interactions, observed in the present study, testify in favor of the above-proposed mechanism of structural reorganization of the associated water phase of the brain, which has the properties of temporary coherence.

References:

- Hus, Y., Segal. Challenges Surrounding the Diagnosis of Autism in Children. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*. 2021; 17: 3509–3529. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S282569>
- Boksha, I.S. Biochemical Abnormalities in Autism. *Autism and Developmental Disorders*. 2005; 3(2): 1–24.
- Boksha, I.S., Prokhorova, T.A., Tereshkina, E.B. et al. Differentiated Approach to Pharmacotherapy of Autism Spectrum Disorders: Biochemical Aspects. *Biochemistry Moscow*. 2023; 88: 303–318. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0006297923030021>
- Maniram J., Karrim S. B., Oosthuizen F., Wiafe E. Pharmacological Management of Core Symptoms and Comorbidities of Autism Spectrum Disorder in Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*. 2022; 18:1629–1644. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S371013>
- Victoria Bamicha, Athanasios Drigas. ToM & ASD: The interconnection of Theory of Mind with the social-emotional, cognitive development of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. The use of ICTs as an alternative form of intervention in ASD. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*. 2022; 33; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6845>
- F. Zhao, X. Zhang, K. -H. Thung, N. Mao, S. -W. Lee and D. Shen. Constructing Multi-View High-Order Functional Connectivity Networks for Diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorder. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*. 2022; 69(3): 1237–1250. doi: 10.1109/TBME.2021.3122813
- Mohammad Ali Salehinejad, Nasim Paknia, Amir Hossein Hosseinpour, Fatemeh Yavari, Carmelo M. Vicario, Michael A. Nitsche, Vahid Nejati. Contribution of the right temporoparietal junction and ventromedial prefrontal cortex to theory of mind in autism: A randomized, sham-controlled tDCS study. *Autism Research*. 2021; 14(8): 1572–1584. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aur.2538>
- Gonçalves, A.M., Monteiro, P. Autism Spectrum Disorder and auditory sensory alterations: a systematic review on the integrity of cognitive and neuronal functions related to auditory processing. *J Neural Transm*. 2023; 130:325–408. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00702-023-02595-9>
- Niesler, B., Kuerten, S., Demir, I.E. et al. Disorders of the enteric nervous system — a holistic view. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2021; 18: 393–410. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41575-020-00385-2>
- Alzubide, S. and Alhalafi, M. () The Gut Brain Connection. *Journal of Behavioral and Brain Science*. 2024; 14: 103–117. doi: 10.4236/jbbs.2024.143008
- Poydasheva, A. G. et al. High-resolution transcranial direct current electrical stimulation (literature review). *Advances in Physiological Sciences*. 2021; 52(1): 3–15.
- Jiujun Qiu, Xuejun Kong, Jihan Li, Jie Yang, Yiting Huang, Minshi Huang, Binbin Sun, Jiayi Su, Helen Chen, Guobin Wan, Jian Kong. Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) over the Left Dorsal Lateral Prefrontal Cortex in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). *Neural Plasticity*. 2021; 19: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6627507>
- Rakhmanin Yu.A., Stekhin A.A., Yakovleva G.V. Biophysics of water: Quantum nonlocality in water treatment technologies, regulatory role of associated water in cellular metabolism, standardization of bioenergetic activity of drinking water. Moscow: Lenand, 2016. – 346 p.
- Stekhin A.A., Yakovleva G.V. Quantum behavior of water: Properties of the electron subsystem of water associates. Electron deficiency as a health risk factor. Moscow: LENAND, 2019. ISBN 978–5–9710–5626–3.
- Pasquale Borrelli, Giovanni Savini, Carlo Cavaliere. Normative values of the topological metrics of the structural connectome: A multi-site reproducibility study across the Italian Neuroscience network. *Physica Medica*. 2023; 112: 102610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2023.102610>
- Y. Yang, C. Ye, X. Guo, T. Wu, Y. Xiang and T. Ma. Mapping Multi-Modal Brain Connectome for Brain Disorder Diagnosis via Cross-Modal Mutual Learning. *EEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*. 2024; 43(1): 108–121. doi: 10.1109/TMI.2023.3294967
- Stekhin A.A., Yakovleva G.V., Kalinina L.A. Wave medicine – an innovative direction in medicine (literature review). *Information medicine / Collection of scientific papers of the scientific and practical conference "Information medicine"*. Ed. by PhD. Mamaeva M.A. – St. Petersburg: Publishing House "Stella". 2024. – 126 p.
- Stekhin A., Yakovleva G., Kalinina L. Wave medicine – an innovative direction in medicine. *Norwegian Journal of Development of the International*

Science No137/2024, 42–49; Danish Scientific Journal No86, 2024, 32–39.

19 Stekhin A.A., Yakovleva G.V., Rakhmanin Yu.A. A systems view of longevity. Water paradigm of life / Ed. Yu.A. Rakhmanin. Moscow: Lenand, 2024. – 252 p.

20 Stekhin A.A. et al. From theory to practice of wave correction of health, pp. 101–105.; Stekhin A.A. and others. Methodology of restorative, preventive and therapeutic medicine based on restoration of wave activity of the primary circuit of intracellular regulation. pp. 196–200. XIV International Symposium “Human Ecology and Medical and Biological Safety of the Population” (Republic of Crimea, Mriya Resort & SPA,

October 19–25, 2024. Collection of materials. – p. 245. M., 2024.

21 Stekhin A.A., Rakhmanin Yu.A., Yakovleva G.V., Iksanova T.I. The role of body water in the etiology of chronic non-infectious diseases (literature review). Hygiene and sanitation. 2021; 100(6): 584–593. <https://doi.org/10.47470/0016-9900-2021-100-6-584-593>

22 Stekhin A.A., Yakovleva G.V., Rachin A.P., Karasev A.K. Wave (quantum) therapy intervertebral disc pp.46–50 / All-Russian Congress of Manual Therapists. Bulletin No. 22.

Moscow: Pero Publishing House, 2023. – 66 p.